

Effect of Consolidation Pressure on Void Reduction and Effective Properties in a Stochastic UHMWPE Fibril Array

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OVERVIEW

Goal: Understand how consolidation process variables Temperature(T), Pressure(P) and time (t) control composite microstructure (*Reduce voids, Increase fiber volume fraction, Minimize filament damage*) to improve composite performance (*Reduce weight, Maintain Performance, Reduce dynamic deflection, Maximize energy absorption*).

- What is the effect of consolidation pressure on the stochastic fibril level microstructure within a fiber at processing temperature?
 - Fibril deformation, shape, and fibril-fibril contact areas.
 - Inter-fibril void content.
- What is the effect of microstructure on the effect properties of the fiber at room temperature?

- Based on AFM imaging, the microstructure of polyethylene (PE) fibers consists of aligned fibrils and interstitial voids. Under hydrostatic pressure, this structure undergoes reformation, directly influencing fiber performance.
- The following objectives are pursued:
 - **Develop** a methodology to correlate consolidation pressure with microstructural evolution.
 - **Predict** inelastic deformation, contact area growth, and progressive void reduction.
 - **Determine** effective isotropic mechanical properties using finite element analysis₂ (FEA).

- **Develop a methodology to apply hydrostatic pressure on a fibril array**
 - Constant diameter
 - Stochastic diameter distribution
- **Use a methodology to predict microstructure evolution.**
- **Define RVE for constant fibril diameter and statistical fibril diameter distribution**
 - Fibril diameter distribution
 - Equivalent interstitial void content
- **Develop methodology to calculate effective properties of the fibril array as a function of hydrostatic pressure/void content**

› **Step 1: Uniform Fibrils Model**

- Used to demonstrate methodology and validate simulation approach
- Enables use of RVE to save computational time

› **Step 2: Statistical Geometry Generation**

- Generated fibril array geometries from statistical fibril diameter data.
- Used the Monte Carlo method to reduce the array size while preserving representative fibril diameter distribution and interstitial void content.

› **Step 3: Realistic Simulation of Fibril Microstructure Subjected to Hydrostatic Pressure During Consolidation at 125C**

- Optimal configuration applied to validated model
- Leads to realistic and accurate predictions with reduced complexity

- The data are based on molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of UHMWPE at sheet process conditions:
- 125 °C over a wide range of consolidation pressure
- According to N. Dewapriya et al. (2023, 2024), the most recent mechanical properties were obtained from MD simulations conducted at a strain rate of $10^9/s$ at 125 °C.
- The yield stresses σ_{ay} , σ_{by} , and τ_{aby} correspond to the a-direction, b-direction, and a–b shear plane, respectively.
- These values were used to define the anisotropic yield behavior.
- This table summarizes the elastic properties used in the plane strain FEA model.

E_a , GPa	E_b , GPa	E_c , GPa	G_{ab} , GPa	G_{bc} , GPa	G_{ca} , GPa
3.346	4.3	263.53	2.78	1.30	1.77
ν_{ab}	ν_{bc}	ν_{ac}	σ_{ay} , GPa	σ_{by} , GPa	τ_{aby} , GPa
0.48	0.006	0.007	0.34	0.093	0.213

Key Steps in Modeling Hydrostatic Pressure on Fibril Arrays

1. Hexagonal Packing and Void Content Estimation

- Select the optimal fibril ring geometry and number of rings to replicate initial void content.
- Perform convergence study to ensure accuracy and model stability (see next slide).

2. Pressure Application Strategy

- Establish a method for uniform hydrostatic pressure application across the external surface of outermost fibril in the array.
- Surround fibrils with an incompressible matrix material to transmit uniform hydrostatic pressure (details in Slide 9).
- All fibril surfaces are frictionless

To reduce computational cost and improve simulation efficiency, the RVE was modeled using one-eighth of the circular fibril array as shown above.

Key Steps in Modeling Hydrostatic Pressure on Fibril Arrays

1- Hexagonal Packing and Void Content Estimation

Table 1. Comparison of void fraction values obtained analytically from Equation (1) and measured using AutoCAD, as a function of the number of fibrils derived from Equation (2).

Number of rings (n)	Void Fraction (Theoretical)	Void Fraction (CAD)	Number of fibrils (N)
1	0.042142104	0.042	7
2	0.06088869	0.0608	19
3	0.069691669	0.069	37
4	0.074742231	0.0747	61
5	0.078007966	0.078	91

- Equations (1) and (2), derived from uniform circular geometry, show excellent agreement with AutoCAD results for $n=1$ to 4, validating their accuracy for larger ring counts.

$$\text{Voids Fraction} = \frac{n^2 \left(\sqrt{3} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right)}{n^2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{3} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) + \pi \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \right)} \dots (1), \text{ } n \text{ is the number of rings}$$

$$N(n) = 1 + 3n(n + 1) \dots (2), \text{ } N \text{ is the number of fibrils}$$

- However, due to computational limitations associated with ABAQUS simulations, and considering that our goal is to approximate the methodology rather than achieve full convergence, selecting two rings is deemed appropriate for the current model.

STEP 1: UNIFORM FIBRILS MODEL

Key Steps in Modeling Hydrostatic Pressure on Fibril Arrays

Constitutive Model for Incompressible Material

- The blue region is modeled using a Mooney–Rivlin hyperelastic material:

Strain Energy Function:

$$U = C_{10} (\bar{I}_1 - 3) + C_{01} (\bar{I}_2 - 3) + (1 / D_1) (J^{el} - 1)^2 \dots (1)$$

Material Constants:

$$\mu_0 = 2 (C_{10} + C_{01}), \quad K_0 = 2 / D_1$$

μ_0 Shear modulus

- The shear modulus was reduced to ensure the matrix can carry the applied pressure without stress relaxation (see Equation 2) based on Ogden, R.W. (1997) and Bonet, J., & Wood, R.D. (2008).

Incompressible Material Cauchy Stress Tensor:

$\sigma = -p I + \mu B \dots (2)$, $B=FF^T$ is the left Cauchy-Green deformation tensor. μ is the shear modulus

- Thus, the lowest value of the shear modulus will ensure the material accurately carries the hydrostatic pressure.

The incompressible matrix material

Fibrils array

Schematic of the micromechanical model.

Element Type for Incompressible Region: ABAQUS

- 3D hybrid elements were used in the finite element model.
- The element type selected is C3D8H, which is appropriate for modeling incompressible materials.
- These elements are ideal for capturing the behavior under uniform hydrostatic pressure.
- The mesh ensures accurate stress transmission through the incompressible matrix to the fibril structure.

Element Type for Fibril Region

- Fibrils were modeled using 3D brick elements (C3D8) with full integration.
- A nonlinear mesh convergence study was conducted to balance accuracy and computational cost.
- Although modeled in 3D, plane strain boundary conditions were applied on surfaces normal to the cross-section.

The void region

Volume Change and Equivalent Property Estimation

For 2D plane strain conditions, the following equations are used to calculate the equivalent mechanical properties:

$$K = -V \frac{dP}{dV} \dots \dots \dots (1) \quad K = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{-P}{E} (1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Based on the extracted data for volume change and strain variation with applied pressure, the following equivalent mechanical properties can be computed:

- **Equivalent Elastic Modulus (E)**
- **Bulk Modulus (K)**
- **Stress–Strain Relationship**

These values are determined by solving the constitutive relations shown in the equations above.

- Equivalent volume representations were computed for both fibrils and voids based on their volumes.
- All final results and visualizations were based on these equivalent circle approximations.

STEP 1: UNIFORM FIBRILS MODEL

- The repeated geometric pattern was constructed using AutoCAD and employed for representative volume element (RVE) micromechanical modeling. Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) were applied to simulate the infinite material response. Additionally, symmetry boundary conditions were imposed along the X-plane and an oblique plane inclined at 30 degrees to the horizontal, as illustrated.

Initial Results: Incompressible Material Response Under Hydrostatic Loading

S11=Radial stresses=Applied pressure

- The **radial stresses** in the incompressible material are **uniform** and match the applied hydrostatic pressure.
- **Shear stresses remain negligible**, confirming the incompressible material behavior.
- These results validate the pressure transfer mechanism and satisfy **Equation (2)** (Ogden, R.W. (1997) and Bonet, J., & Wood, R.D. (2008)) $\sigma = -p I + \mu B \dots\dots (2)$

Void Reduction and Deformation Stages at 125C

- In the MD configuration, complete void elimination occurs at an applied pressure of approximately **250 MPa (1% void content is achieved at 160 MPa)**.
- The void reduction process can be categorized into **three distinct stages**:
 - **Elastic deformation (0 to 50 MPa)**
 - **Elastic-plastic softening (50 to 150 MPa)**
 - **Bulk modulus stiffening (150 to 250 MPa)**
- The initial void fraction for the uniform fiber array with two rings is **6.31%**.
- The structure undergoes **inelastic deformation** until a fully void-free configuration is achieved at 250 MPa.

Plane Strain Bulk Modulus vs. Void Content at 125C

The bulk modulus was calculated from the volume-pressure plot, considering the equivalent volume changes of the fibrils and voids.

$$K = -V \frac{dP}{dV} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

At an initial void content of 6.3%, the bulk modulus is at its minimum value of 1101.8 MPa. As pressure increases, voids collapse and stiffness rises. When the void fraction approaches zero, the bulk modulus rapidly increases and converges toward the fully dense value of 55,750 MPa, as predicted by Equation (2). This trend is clearly shown in the plot, where the bulk modulus increases sharply as porosity diminishes.

$$K = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Effective Stress-Strain of the model under hydrostatic pressure

The effective elastic strain response exhibits a typical three-stage behavior: an initial elastic regime, a plateau region, and a final densification phase. Densification occurs at a lower strain due to the influence of the bulk modulus.

STEP 1: UNIFORM FIBRILS MODEL

The normalized elastic modulus was compared to the analytical inverse correlation proposed by Ji et al. (2006) for the effect of porosity on mechanical properties:

$E/E_0 = (1 - P)^{\frac{1}{J}}$, where P is the void content and J is the fractal parameter. A value of $J=0.04$ provided the best correlation with the data.

- The elastic modulus at **zero porosity** tends to match the modulus of the **constituent material** used in the simulation or experiment.

**Morphology of
UHMWPE Fiber
(McDaniel et al.,
2015)**

- AFM imaging reveals aligned fibrils with interstitial voids in PE fibers.
- Surface fibrils show width variations following a log-normal distribution.
- Direct measurements validate the statistical trend across the fiber surface.
- This distribution serves as a baseline for structural modeling.

STEP 2: STATISTICAL GEOMETRY GENERATION

Efficient Modeling Through Monte Carlo and CAD

CAD/VBA Modeling Output

We applied Monte Carlo sampling to statistical fibril data and used CAD to generate ten configurations for each case.

The 25-fibril model balanced accuracy and efficiency, reducing simulation time by over 86% compared to the full model.

STEP 3: REALISTIC SIMULATION

- One representative geometry out of ten configurations was selected for detailed FE simulation.

- Based on CAD-generated distributions, multiple fibril array configurations were created.
- Among these, one configuration was selected for finite element modeling in ABAQUS.
- Configuration 2, characterized by the largest initial void content, was chosen to represent the most critical case for assessing consolidation and mechanical response

- Schematic of the model for 25-fibril arrays with initial voids of 9.48%.
- The red-dash line is the equivalent radius for the fibrils and voids with equivalent volume.

STEP 3: REALISTIC SIMULATION

•The results: Contour plots.

•The same modeling approach used for the uniform fibril array was applied to the stochastic configuration. However, in this case, hydrostatic pressure was applied uniformly along the entire circumference of the fibril array to accurately simulate realistic compaction behavior. Voids gradually decrease with increasing pressure. Complete void-free occurs at 166 MPa.

STEP 3: REALISTIC SIMULATION

- Void's content reduction with increasing hydrostatic pressure at 125C

- Initial void content is 9.48% (0.0948) is much closer to the measured porosity
- Three stages of the plots (Elastic deformation, Elastic-plastic softening, Bulk modulus stiffening) exist.
- Hydrostatic pressure of 160 MPa reduced Void Content to 1% for the Stochastic fibril array (9.48% to 1%). In comparison, 160MPa reduced Void Content from 6.3% to 1%).

Predicted evolution of microstructure for Stochastic fibril array is more realistic (fibril shape, contact and relative orientation of PE crystals) for FFA simulations considering fibrillation failure modes

➤ The results :Bulk Modulus Evolution During Void Elimination , Based on MD at 125C Input

- For the plane strain condition, the effective bulk modulus K is calculated from the volumetric strain vs. pressure plot using the relation:
$$K = -\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta V/V} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$
- Analytically, the bulk modulus of the fully dense constituent material (from MD input properties) is determined from Equation (2):
$$K = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$
- Substituting the MD-derived values yields: $K=56.1$ GPa
- As void content vanishes, the effective bulk modulus approaches that of the solid, confirming pressure-induced densification and stiffness recovery.

STEP 3: REALISTIC SIMULATION

- The results: The equivalent stress-strain, Based on MD at 125C
Input

- Effective stress-strain computed at the red-dotted effective circle, it can be seen that the stages are Elastic deformation, Elastic-plastic softening, Bulk modulus stiffening.

The results: Effective elastic modulus, Based on MD at 125C Input

- At an initial void content of 9.48%, the elastic modulus was 1115.9 MPa. As voids diminished, stiffness increased steadily, reaching 3345 MPa at zero porosity. The void-free modulus closely matches the solid input property, confirming the correlation.

- A novel micromechanical model was developed to simulate the effect of consolidation pressure on polyethylene (PE) fibril arrays with interstitial voids.
- The model incorporates fibril distribution and void content inspired by AFM imaging.
- A Mooney–Rivlin hyperelastic model successfully represented the incompressible polymer, transmitting uniform hydrostatic pressure.
- Parametric studies confirmed the model's ability to capture inelastic fibril deformation, void collapse, and contact area growth.
- The evolved microstructure provides a realistic basis for multiscale modeling of fibril interaction and compaction behavior.
- The methodology enables prediction of effective mechanical properties as functions of microstructural change.
- Plane strain bulk modulus, Young's modulus, and stress–strain response show nonlinear increases with pressure.
- As voids are eliminated, the effective properties approach those of fully dense fibrils.

Future Work:

- Use the predicted microstructure to evaluate effective mechanical properties at room temperature (RT).
- Apply the predicted contact areas between fibrils to model defibrillation behavior under axial and transverse loading conditions.

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